

ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE POLLUTION IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES: A CASE STUDY OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR, CALABAR, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The investigation comprised acoustical and social surveys using the University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria, which shares similar characteristics with many other Nigerian Universities as a case study. The acoustical survey involved wide-range of measurements of vehicle volume, composition and noise levels in over 100 points while questionnaires/interviews were used/conducted in the social survey. A total hourly traffic volume entering the University of Calabar through the Main Gate during noisy period was 2442 in the categories of heavies and buses (0.6%), cars (15.6%) and motorcycles (83.8%). Noise levels exceeded or equated for 10% of the measurement time period of 1 hour, L_{10} (1h), were calculated to be 69.7 and 70.9 dB (A) for assumed average vehicle speeds of 20 and 40km/h respectively. Outdoor day-night noise levels, L_{dn} , were also calculated for the daytime and nighttime periods with a maximum value of 81.7 dB (A). Maximum indoor noise levels, L_{max} , were measured for quiet and noisy periods as 43.0-46.4 dB (A) and 63.5-76.0 dB (A) respectively while outdoor L_{max} for quiet and noisy periods were respectively measured to be 43.7-48.0 dB (A) and 60.0-88.0 dB (A). Temporal noise characteristics plotted for various parts of the University of Calabar for quiet periods and the noise spectrum were fairly flat while fluctuations with peaks and dips characterized temporal plots for noisy periods. Results of social survey showed that noise heard always was that of adults followed by that of road traffic. It was found that the University of Calabar community is very sensitive to noise and that headache constituted the greatest effect of this menace while the least was fatigue.

KEYWORDS: Environmental noise pollution, Nigerian Universities, acoustical survey and noise levels.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental noise is any undesired (unwanted) sound that constitutes a menace to the environment. It is sound at the wrong time and in the wrong place. Environmental noise is as a result of human attitude and is increasing with industrialization and urbanization. Noise is nothing new! The poet, Decimus Junius Juveniles, commented on conditions in ancient Rome and stated that noise caused more death among the Roman invalids than any other factor. Today, in addition to the noise of modern traffic, we have to endure deafening tumult from a multitude of modern 'mass-produced mechanical noise makers' (Gorlin, 1976). Studies (Cookers and Price, 1975; Izumi and Yano, 1991; Onuu, 2000a and 2000b) have shown that environmental noise poses a multi-dimensional urban challenge. It constitutes a major public health nuisance having far-reaching and wide-ranging effects. For example, environmental noise pollution causes ear-damage. A short period exposure of more than 90 dB can damage

the ear immediately. Tiny hairs in the hearing mechanism are destroyed and never to grow again. Environmental noise pollution also causes physical ailments, stress in learning process and let down in workers productivity (Wood, 1983). There is also indication that noise adversely affects the heart and blood vessels causing high blood pressure and increase in cholesterol level (Wood, 1983). Sudden noise such as car backfiring can cause a jump in pulse rate. Noise also sets nerves on edge. It produces stress emotionally and physically. Other health effects of noise include vasoconstriction, changes in heart beat rate, muscular activity, metabolic rate, slow sleep breathing, an increase in gastrointestinal mobility, diastolic pressure, respiratory rates, blood glucose, and urinary 17-ketosteroid and decrease in salivary and gastric secretion, slowing of digestive functions, etc. (Wood, 1983).

Environmental noise pollution has become very worrisome in Nigerian Universities. In acoustical and social surveys (Onuu, 2000b) developed

cross-city response characteristics of road traffic noise and found that 34% percent of the respondents complained that they were most annoyed by the noise of road traffic during reading/studying. The high environmental noise climate in Nigerian Universities negates the reason for their establishment. A University is a centre of knowledge whose goals and objectives are teaching, research and public service. Universities are important agents in the development of human resources of any nation. These major roles of Universities in the national development are achieved through their programmes of teaching, learning and research under a healthy academic environment. However, the environment of Nigerian Universities have changed with stringent economic conditions and rising enrolment that have resulted in over-crowding of few available facilities (Abegaz, 1975). Whenever people are over-crowded in a community, the noise made by some disturbs others. Thus, one man's music is another man's noise. University communities are now subjected to the confused noise of cars, motorcycles and buses and their horns, sirens, the roars of planes, noise from hawkers, generators and students themselves. All these have given rise to an unhealthy environment, which makes working, leisure, learning and studying, teaching difficult, and, sometimes impossible.

It is true that environmental noise studies have been conducted in this country, but no serious survey known to the authors has been specifically dedicated to the University of Calabar or to any Nigerian University for that matter. The study at Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria by Onuu (2000c) was on sound (noise) characteristics. Thus, the noise levels in the University of Calabar and other Nigerian Universities and the attitude of members of the University Community towards this environmental nuisance remained poorly known. Attempts have, however, been made at the Federal level to control noise in Nigeria. On Monday, April 26, 1982 the House of Representatives Committee on Housing, Community Development and Environment, in a bold step towards the control and abatement of environmental noise in Nigeria, called for memoranda from the public on *Noise Pollution*

Urban Noise Control Measures on the Federal Environmental Bill, 1981 (Onuu, 2001). More recently, the Nigerian Senate began debate on a bill to ban the use of siren (Onuu, 2001) because the killing of some people was caused by wrong use of siren by some Government functionaries. Apart from the fact that measured sound pressure levels emitted by siren are as high as 130 dB (A) which damages the ear, siren poses a lot of traffic danger to pedestrians and other road users as many recent accidents in Nigeria involving road traffic are attributable to its reckless use along our highways and within cities. This has recently led to the submission of a proposal on training for the minimization of road traffic danger, air and noise pollution to the Federal Road Safety Corps, Nigeria (Onuu, 2002). Unfortunately, these attempts to reduce noise by Governments are not pursued to their logical conclusion as noise has continued to be a major environmental pollutant in Nigeria and community reactions high. Recently, Onuu (2000d) reported that 75.7% of Nigerian community respondents interviewed admitted that they were annoyed (worried) by noise. Onuu (2000d) attributed this large number affected to high poverty level; unemployment rate; citing of airports close to schools, hospitals and residential homes; poor and inefficient transportation system; wide-range use of standby plants and generators because of inefficient functioning of the National Electric Power Authority, (NEPA), etc. which are reasons for the general deterioration of the health of Nigerians and the quality of their environment caused by environmental noise. Noise annoyance study (Onuu, 2000e) has shown that 44.3% of the people interviewed in South-Eastern Nigeria responded that they were most annoyed (worried) in schools, places of study and work by road traffic noise, a problem that is over a thousand times greater than before a society became motorized. There is, therefore, no doubt that noise needs to be controlled and abated in Nigeria (Menkiti, 1976; Menkiti, 1982 and Onuu, 2000f). In fact, it was to control and abate environmental noise in Nigeria that the University of Calabar entered a joint programme with the Nigerian building and Road Research Institute, NBRRI.

To commence any effective noise control in Nigeria the following questions (Onuu and

Menkiti, 1990) should be addressed: Do we have anti-noise laws and ordinances in Nigeria? If we have, how do we come about them? How does Government treat acoustical matters that bother on noise? Are we really interested in research that will lead to the control of environmental noise (a nuisance) that has been variously described as *one of life's great stressors* Makis Tsapogas, adviser to the World Health Organization; *America's most pervasive pollutant* The Boston Sunday Globe, U.S.A. and *The worst pollutant of our time* Daily Express, London, even in our Universities?

Therefore, with the upsurge in the menace of noise as environmental nuisance and recent renewal to control same, it has become necessary to conduct detailed acoustical and social surveys that will form the basis of control of environmental noise pollution in Nigerian Universities and others with similar features. The objectives of this study is, therefore, to accumulate data on environmental noise in the University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State in the Federal Republic of Nigeria, and attitude of workers and students, analyze them and recommend measures for abatement and control. The results of this investigation will also be useful in the formulation of anti-noise laws, ordinances and other acoustical matters that bother on noise.

2. ABOUT THE UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR

The University of Calabar located in Calabar, Cross River State in the Federal Republic of Nigeria grew, out of the Calabar Campus of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. As a campus of the University of Nigeria, it began functioning during the 1973/74 academic year with only 154 students and a small cadre of academic, administrative and technical staff.

At inception, the University of Calabar, Calabar, had three faculties and a total student population of 515. But as at the current academic year, 2002/2003, student population has increased to about 30,000 becoming, probably, the most populous University in Nigeria. Thus, Libraries, classrooms, laboratories, studios and workshops are usually overcrowded. Presently, the University of Calabar has 63 academic

departments, 10 faculties, 4 colleges and institutes as well as many non-academic departments and units. In the University of Calabar there are over 2,500 teaching and non-teaching staff. Some measures have been put in place by the management to drastically reduce student's population. One of such measures is the gradual phasing out of Diploma programmes. Some *abandoned* lecture halls and office blocks have been completed and new lecture halls built. The last measure has recently attracted commendation by the Federal Government.

Apart from annexes in town, the University of Calabar has two major campuses that are close to each other. These are the Main Campus (also called the Duke Town Campus) and the New Library Campus. These campuses house offices and lecture halls. The University of Calabar has a good network of roads and is adjudged the cleanest University in Nigeria. A double lane road with median strips separates the two major campuses on which are planted shrubs and flowers. The shrubs and flowers absorb noise of certain audio frequencies and also beautify the environment. Post-graduate students' hostels are located at the Main Campus while undergraduate students' hostels are located away from the two campuses but still within the University. The University of Calabar Staff Quarters (Old and New) are located about 1.5 km from each of the campuses. The roads to the Staff Quarters are double-laned. Behind the Main (New or the University) Library is the tributary of the Cross River. To the west of the University of Calabar is the International Airport. Although the University of Calabar is not directly under any fly-over path at low flying altitudes, aircraft noise could be heard in the University especially during landing and take-off of aircraft.

The President and Command-in-Chief of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, commissioned the Calabar Free Trade Zone (CFTZ) in November, 2001. Since then, there has been an upsurge of used motor vehicles popularly referred to as *tokumbo* or *Belgium* in Calabar town and its environs including the University. Some construction work has been going-on in the New Library Campus of the University as the new lecture halls pavilions and offices are being constructed and buildings which have been

abandoned for a very long time are being completed. Business centres which provide services to the University of Calabar community have increased as workers and neighbouring communities struggle to make-ends meet. It is not uncommon, therefore, to see hawkers who proclaim their goods at designated points within the University. Some departments and owners of some business centres resort to the use of electric generators to provide electricity in the event of failure of the National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) to supply electricity. Thus, it becomes very obvious why the environmental noise climate has risen in the University of Calabar and other Nigerian Universities.

3. METHODOLOGY, NOISE LEVEL INDICES AND ANALYSIS

The study comprised physical measurements and social surveys involving interviews and the use of questionnaires.

3.1. PHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS

Measurements of noise levels were made using the precision sound level meter (Bruel and Kjaer) Type 2203 with an octave filter (B&K) Type 1613 attached. Hourly traffic volume and composition were determined using stopwatch. Percentage composition was also determined. During measurements, the microphone was directed towards the noise source and the meter was held away from the body. The least distance between the microphone and noise source was 5m. Measurements of noise levels were made at facades of the Main Library, classrooms and lecture halls, laboratories, workshops and offices facing the noise source. In these cases, the microphone was held 1m from the facades. Noise level measurements were made outside and inside buildings with windows open. The microphone was held at the distance of 1.2 m above the ground, which is the approximate average ear-ground distance for a human being. Measurements were made at over 100 points at noisy (peak) and quiet periods during the day (0700-0200) and during the night (2200-0700). The sites where measurements were made were open, level and in congested/free-flow road traffic conditions when road-traffic was the major noise source. From the series of measurements, the sound pressure level, which is equaled or

exceeded for 10% of the time period of 1 hour, $L_{10}(h)$, given by the expression:

$$L_{10}(h) = 10 \log(q) + 33 \log(v + 40 + 500/v) + 10 \log(1 + 5p/v) - 27.6 \text{ dB}(A) \quad (1)$$

where q is the number of vehicles/hour during the time, p is the ratio of heavy vehicles to the total number and v is the vehicle speed in km/h, and day-night noise level L_{dn} :

$$L_{dn} = 10 \log \frac{1}{24} (15 \times 10^{L_d/10} + 9 \times 10^{(L_n+10)/10}) \quad (2)$$

where L_d is the noise level during the day-time (0700-2200) and L_n is the noise level during the night-time (2200-0700) periods were calculated. L_{max} was also measured.

3.2. SOCIAL SURVEY

The social survey involved the use of questionnaires and interviews. A total of 2,510 were contacted. The questionnaire consisted of 31 items with options from which respondents were asked to choose. The first part of the questionnaire/interview consisted of personal, non-noise and demographic information on sex, residential address, department, status (staffs or student), income, type of building as office and residence, length of time as a staff or student, approximate distance from office, laboratory, classroom or workshop to the nearest motorway or major noise source, ownership of car, motorcycle, business centre in the University of Calabar, etc. Before noise was gradually introduced the interviewer wanted to know if the respondent has some hearing problem. Some of the items and option are: Do you have problem with hearing? (a) Yes (b) No. If yes, do you use any hearing aid? (a) Yes (b) No. How was your previous residential area? (a) Extremely quiet (b) Very quiet (c) Quiet (d) Not very quiet (e) Noisy (f) Very noisy (g) Extremely noisy. What type of noise is most prevalent in your office, classroom or the library in University of Calabar? (a) Road traffic (b) Aircraft (c) Adults (d) Children (e) Animals (f) Construction (g) Generator (h) Air-conditioner (i) Any other, please specify..... . Where do you spend most of your time in the University of Calabar? (a) Classrooms (b) Libraries (c) Offices (d) Laboratories (e) Any other, please specify..... . Is where you spend most of your time facing a motorway? (a) Yes (b) No. Further, the interviewer wanted to know if

respondent's activities in the University of Calabar are usually disrupted by noise and the type of noise heard always in the University. The question "How does noise affect you?" was included as an item.

Items on complaint and complaint actions were also included in the questionnaire. Such items included: Have you complained to any authority about noise level in the University of Calabar? If No, why did you not complain? If you did, to whom? Was any action taken by those you complained to? The last items concerned control of noise in the University of Calabar and included: Do you want environmental noise in the University of Calabar controlled? Would you want to control it by yourself? What do you want the authorities to do about noise in the University of Calabar?

Percentage composition was also determined. The number of people and the percentages responding to options in each item of the questionnaire were determined.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. PHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS

Total hourly traffic volume entering the University of Calabar through the Main Gate during a noisy (peak) period and their composition were found to be 2442 in the categories heavies and buses (15,0.6%), cars (381,15.6%) and motorcycles (2,046,83.8%). These data were used to calculate sound pressure levels which were equaled or exceeded for 10% of the measurement time period of 1 hour using eqn.1. This gave SPL values of 69.7 and 70.9 dB (A) for average vehicle speeds of 20 and 40km/h respectively. Outdoor day-night levels, L_{dn} , were calculated in the University of Calabar using the data in Table 1. These varied from a minimum of 71.9 to a maximum of 81.7 dB (A). Noise levels emitted by electric generators operating within the University varied from 83 to 90 dB (A). Table 1 shows maximum noise levels, L_{max} , at various locations in the University of Calabar. A minimum indoor L_{max} for quiet period of 43.0 and a maximum of 48.0 dB (A) were measured (Table 1). Table 1 also shows minimum and maximum outdoor values of L_{max} for noisy (peak) period of 63.5 and

84.0 dB (A) respectively. L_{max} in churches were as high as 100 dB (A) sometimes. Temporal noise characteristics have been plotted for some major points in the University of Calabar (Figures 1-4). Figure 5 shows noise spectrum in the University of Calabar. The total number of vehicles per hour as measured at a point in Calabar, close to the University Main Gate, in an earlier investigation (Onuu, 2000a) was 2376. Their percentage composition was also found to be heavies (1.2%), buses (5.1%), cars (25.4%) and motorcycles (68.3%).

Table 1: *Maximum noise levels at various locations in the University of Calabar

S/No.	Location	L_{max} for quiet period (dB(A))		L_{max} for noisy period (dB(A))	
		Indoor	Outdoor	Indoor	Outdoor
1	Physics Lab. 1	44.0	46.0	74.2	77.0
2	Chemistry Lab. 1	44.0	45.0	64.5	68.0
3	Geology Lab. 1	43.5	43.7	65.0	67.0
4	Biological Sciences (Room 222)	43.5	43.9	68.0	75.0
5	New Science Lecture (NSLT) 1	45.5	48.0	65.5	77.0
6	NSLT 2	46.0	47.5	66.0	75.0
7	New Library (NL.) (Room 201)	46.5	48.0	67.0	75.5
8	NL (Room 202)	43.5	44.0	74.0	75.0
9	Law Lecture Room	46.5	47.5	76.0	79.0
10	Physiology Lab.	43.0	44.0	75.0	77.0
11	Faculty of Arts Lecture Complex	45.0	46.5	64.0	69.5
12	New Art Theatre (NAT)	43.8	44.2	65.0	69.0
13	Lecture Room 202, Main Campus	45.5	48.5	67.0	75.0
14	DBA Lecture Hall	43.5	44.0	74.0	88.0
15	Theatre Arts Display Hall, Main Campus	43.5	44.0	63.5	69.5
16	ETF Lecture Complex	43.8	47.0	57.0	66.0
17	Computer Centre, open space	-	46.5	-	84.0

* All indoor measurements were made with windows open.

The results of the present study show a total increase of 2.7% in the number of vehicles per hour. This increase could be attributed to upsurge in the number of vehicles in Calabar, Nigeria in recent times particularly after the commissioning of the Calabar Free Trade Zone (CFTZ) in Calabar through which motor vehicles are brought into the country in addition to a few other sources. Motorcycles are the major means of vehicle transportation in Nigeria with measured noise levels in the range 74 to 86 dB (A). The reason for this is the few number of bus and taxi routes in Calabar, in particular, the time saved even though road transportation by motorcycle is expensive and risky. The composition of motorcycles in this investigation is very significant and the increase, 18.5%, worthy of note. McNulty (1987) carried out noise measurements in the new industrialized countries of Malaysia, Singapore and the Republic of Korea and observed that a feature of the individual classes

of road transportation is the predominance of motorcycles. It was concluded that the competitive climate of the motorcycle industry obviates the possibility of any radical reduction of the present levels despite exhortation to manufacturers of motorcycles to design-out noise (McNulty, 1987). In 135 school in Korea and Malaysia, McNulty, 1987). found that 50% and 10% of respondents suffer an average of 68 and 75 dB (A) of the equivalent noise level during the working school day respectively owing to traffic noise and that noise levels inside classrooms ranged between 55 and 79 dB (A) even though the recommended sound level in classrooms is 45 dB (A) for reasonable communication. According to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 1973), for levels of 70 dB (A) only 45% of sentence intelligibility is possible. From Table 1 which shows some noise exposure levels, it is clear that in most of the classrooms in the University of Calabar more than 45% sentence intelligibility is achieved since indoor noise levels measured in such rooms are less than 70 dB (A). Previous roadside noise measurements (Onuu, 2000b) within schools showed L_{10} ranging from 74.5 dB (A) for a site in Calabar to 81.0 dB (A) for a site in Port-Harcourt.

Although noise characteristics at various points in the University of Calabar were reasonably steady at about 45 dB (A) during quiet period, some fluctuations ($L_{max} = \pm 25$ dB) were observed with peaks and dips (Figures 1, 3 and 4). The temporal noise characteristic for noisy period at the Pedestrian Gate was fairly flat (Figure 2). The reason for this is the dominance of vehicles whose engines are steaming and in start/stop conditions. At this gate, there is hardly free-flow of vehicles especially at noisy periods. It is known in environmental noise pollution studies that fluctuation of temporal noise plots is directly proportional to annoyance, activity interference and similar effects which noise causes to community residents. Maximum fluctuation was measured/observed at the University Library (New Library) which is usually congested with road traffic and human beings as some business centres serving the University community are located at some points within the Library building. This maximum fluctuation could result from the reflections from the New Library complex building

and other objects resulting in increased sound level and a reverberant sound field. Also, the spectrum of noise in the University of Calabar is fairly flat implying that the noise does not dominate any particular frequency (Figure 5).

4.2 SOCIAL SURVEY

Figure 6 shows noise heard always in the University of Calabar. Disruption of activity by noise and noise rating of the University of Calabar are shown in Figures 7 and 8 respectively while Figure 9 shows the effect of noise in the University of Calabar community. Forty-five percent of the members of the University community contacted responded that the noise heard always is that made by adults. Other responses are noise of road traffic (19.85%), aircraft (11.1%), children (7.7%), generator (6.9%), air-conditioner (4.7%), others (4.7%), animals (0.7%) and construction (0.7%) (Figure 6). Percentage responses in respect of disruption of activities by noise in the University of Calabar (Figure 7) are slightly (36.0), not very much (31.2), not at all (15.1), much (10.7) and very much (6.8). These responses have shown the imperturbable, the super-(hypersensitive) groups and those members of the University community in the median response category. A situation where up to 17.5% of University community respondents reported much disruption of activities by noise should start to be of serious concern. The implication, however, is that although noise levels in the University of Calabar are low compared to those in some other schools outside Nigeria, members of the University community are very sensitive to noise. Five hundred and twenty-four members of the University of Calabar community representing 40.1% of the respondents contacted rated the noise in University of Calabar as not very quiet. This was followed by 27.5% who rated the University as noisy. From Figure 8, it could be seen that, at least, 87% of the respondents rated the University of Calabar not very quiet while no fewer than 46.9% rated it was noisy. Analysis of the results has further shown that noise has various effects on the University of Calabar community including headache (21.9%), irritation (17.2%), interference (17.1%), annoyance (16.3%), others (12.3%), sleep disturbance

Fig.1: Temporal characteristics of noise at the Main Gate, University of Calabar.

Fig.4: Temporal noise characteristics at Main Library, University of Calabar.

Fig.2: Temporal characteristics of noise at the Pedestrian Gate, University of Calabar.

Fig.5: Noise spectrum of the University of Calabar.

Fig.3: Temporal characteristics at Main Campus (Park), University of Calabar.

Fig.6: Noise heard always in the University of Calabar.

Fig.8: Noise rating of the University of Calabar.

Fig.9: Effect of noise to the University of Calabar Community.

(9.0%) and fatigue (7.2%) (Figure 9). Noise controlled in the University of Calabar was 82.6 while 43.9% of them wanted to control the environmental noise themselves. Members of the churches on campus interviewed responded that although noise levels generated by the musical instruments and the congregation during offertory, praise and worship sections were high, they were not annoyed or disturbed because they were always gathered in the presence of the Lord to rejoice because of their salvation and in their own security. This investigation has further revealed that: response and reaction to noise does not depend on sex and length of stay in ones present residence. Similar result was obtained for sex for road traffic noise (Onuu,2000b). However, there was evidence of limited adaptation with community respondents who had lived up to 15 years and above in their previous residences. Although the relationship between composite noise and adaptation of respondents is not known, the effects of road traffic noise are consistent over time as there no evidence of adaptation over 17-22 years and evidence of only limited adaptation over 7-9 years (Weintein,

1982, and Griffiths and Roy, 1987). Respondents reported that annoyance constituted the greatest affect of noise on them followed by irritation and interference. On interference of noise on activity on various members of the University of Calabar, the percentage responses were as follows: students (19.8) lecturers, ASUU memebers (19.5), senior non-academic staff, SSANU members (17.0) and junior non-academic staff, NASU members (15.6). Thus, members of Non-Academic Staff Union of Universities, NASU, the junior staff reported least interference. This result should be expected, although the percentage, 15.6, is still significant in comparison with responses by other members of the University community. Further, there was no income bias with respect to the members of the University community response to noise. An average of 26-49% of the respondents in the 6 income classes responded that the University is not very quiet, 18-27% that the University of Calabar is noisy and 7-25.2% that the institution is very noisy. This result is surprising but goes to strengthen our findings in this investigation that the difference in percentage response between high income class of the members of the University community (ASUU and SSANU members) and low income class (NASU) is just about 3.9.

On complaint actions, 28.9% complained to colleagues while 15.9% of them took action after complaining. Percentage of respondents who wanted noise controlled in the University of Calabar was 82.6 while 43.9% wanted to control the environmental noise themselves. This strengthens the assertion that the University of Calabar community is very sensitive to noise. About 51% of the lecturers responded to the item with five ratings that they did not complain because they did not want to worry themselves, 34% of SSANU members said they did not complain for the same reason while 22.8% of the students responded that they did not know they had the right to complain.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1. RECOMMENDATIONS

The investigation has led to the following recommendations that will result in control and abatement of increasing environmental noise levels in Nigerian Universities.

1. Universities should establish noise control sections in their environmental units. These sections will specifically see to the control and abatement of noise in Universities.
2. Departments, faculties and institutes should be encouraged to maintain *noise-free* environments in their Universities. This can be done by awarding prizes to the cleanest unit as far as noise is concerned.
3. Universities should, through noise control sections of their environmental units, organize seminars for members of the University community, from time to time.
4. Universities should designate locations for hawkers and vendors where they should stay, proclaim and sell their goods.
5. Universities should establish traffic control units and car parks. This will help direct traffic, reduce traffic congestion and control the use of horns and sirens.
6. Speed limits should be set for vehicles plying the University.
7. Speed breakers should be placed at various points on the roads in Universities. This will check speeds of motor vehicles and reduce noise levels they emit.
8. Governments should institute awards to Universities that are free from environmental noise pollution.
9. Electric generators and other machines that generate noise should be housed far away from classrooms, lecture halls, laboratories, libraries and offices.
10. The use of *noiseless* air-conditioners should be encouraged by Universities.
11. Libraries, classrooms, lecture halls and academic blocs should be cited at places where noise levels and noise intensities are minimum.

12. Vehicles that emit high noise levels should be banned from entering the Universities.
13. Trees and shrubs should be planted between motor parks on campuses and libraries, classrooms, lecture halls and studios.
14. Stadium and play ground, recreation clubs, hostels, staff quarters should be cited far away from classrooms and lecture halls, libraries, studios and laboratories.
15. Universities should promulgate noise control laws and ordinances and enforce them.
16. Universities should sponsor research and encourage linkages in the field of environmental noise.

5.2. CONCLUSION

The results of the acoustical and social surveys have led to the conclusion that although environmental noise poses a serious threat and bodes ill to Nigerian Universities, noise levels inside classrooms are lower than those measured in the new industrialized countries and sentence intelligibility is still kept as low as 45% in most locations within the Universities. The University of Calabar community is very sensitive to noise. Temporal noise characteristics are fairly steady for quiet periods while they show appreciable fluctuation for noisy (peak) periods with peaks and dips characterizing them. Noise spectrum was also reasonably steady. Response to noise does not depend on sex and income and there was no evidence or limited evidence of adaptation with respect to reaction to noise. Respondents that wanted environmental noise to be controlled were more than four-fifths while over two-fifths wanted to control the noise themselves implying that members of the University of Calabar community are very sensitive to noise and worrisome about it.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

- Fig.1: Temporal noise characteristics at the Main Gate, University of Calabar.
- Fig.2: Temporal noise characteristics at the Pedestrian Gate, University of Calabar.
- Fig.3: Temporal noise characteristics at Main Campus Park, University of Calabar.
- Fig.4: Temporal noise characteristics at Main Library, University of Calabar.
- Fig.5: Noise Spectrum of the University of Calabar.
- Fig. 6: Noise heard always in the University of Calabar.
- Fig. 7: Disruption of activities by noise in the University of Calabar.
- Fig. 8: Noise rating by the University of Calabar community.
- Fig.9: Effect of noise to the University of Calabar community.